

PICSE: Procurement Innovation for Cloud Services in Europe

*Funded under the EU Framework Programme for Research and innovation H2020
- Grant Agreement no: 644014*

Deliverable Title: D3.1 Procurement Barriers Report

Submission Due Date: M6 (March 2015)

Actual Submission Date:

Work Package: WP3

Responsible Partner: CSA

Distribution: Public

Nature: Report

Abstract: The purpose of this document is to identify a comprehensive inventory of known barriers to procurement of cloud services for the research community and the public sector. This report will be used as an input for the follow-on PICSE deliverable on Procurement Good Practices.

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Project

<i>Project acronym:</i>	PICSE
<i>Project full title:</i>	Procurement Innovation for Cloud Services in Europe
<i>Project start:</i>	1 October 2014
<i>Project duration:</i>	18 months
<i>Call:</i>	ICT-35-2014: Innovation and Entrepreneurship Support
<i>Grant agreement no.:</i>	644014

Document

<i>Deliverable number:</i>	D3.1
<i>Deliverable title:</i>	Procurement Barriers Report
<i>Author(s):</i>	Cloud Security Alliance
<i>Work package no.:</i>	WP3
<i>Work package title:</i>	Competence
<i>Work package leader:</i>	Cloud Security Alliance
<i>Work package participants:</i>	CERN, CSA, Trust-IT, PICSE Task Force
<i>Distribution:</i>	Public
<i>Nature:</i>	Report

DISCLAIMER

PICSE (644014) is a Coordination and Support Action funded by the EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Horizon 2020. The PICSE Procurers' Platform will give access to a unique repository of information supporting the move from outright purchase to 'pay-per-usage' made possible by the arrival of cloud computing. It builds on the Helix Nebula collaboration between supply and demand of which the three PICSE partners are key members.

This document contains information on PICSE core activities, findings and outcomes and it may also contain contributions from distinguished experts who contribute to PICSE. Any reference to content in this document should clearly indicate the authors, source, organisation and publication date. The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the PICSE consortium and cannot be considered to reflect the views of the European Commission.

CHANGE LOG

Issue	Date	Description	Author/Partner
0.1	10/12/2014	Document structure and Initial Content	Marina Bregou, Daniele Catteddu, CSA
0.2	12/01/2015	First draft with general sections covered	Marina Bregou, CSA
0.3	20/01/2015	Addressing comments by the consortium	Marina Bregou, CSA
0.4	27/02/2015	Analysing the survey results	Marina Bregou, Damir Savanovic, CSA
0.5	09/03/2015	Internal review	Daniele Catteddu, CSA
0.6	07/04/2014	Incorporating consortium second round of comments	Marina Bregou, Damir Savanovic, CSA
0.7	13/04/2015	Trust-IT review	Sara Garavelli, TRUST-IT
0.8	15/04/2015	Incorporating consortium comments	Marina Bregou, Daniele Catteddu, Damir Savanovic, CSA
0.9	23/04/2015	Incorporating Task Force comments	Marina Bregou, Damir Savanovic, CSA
1.0	13/05/2015	Incorporating consortium comments	Marina Bregou, CSA
1.1	27/05/2015	Incorporating consortium comments	Marina Bregou, CSA
1.2	03/06/2016	Fixed figures numbering and graphs Added explanation on the exploitation of survey data	Damir Savanovic, CSA Rachida Amsaghrou, CERN

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Executive Summary

The acquisition of IT services is key to any public or private organisation and the advent of cloud computing requires innovation in the procurement of cloud services.

Although cloud computing has become increasingly popular, it appears that potential customers, in the public sector in general and in the research community in particular, are facing barriers that inhibit the wider adoption of cloud services.

This report presents a list of barriers to cloud services procurement identified through literature, in-depth interviews of IT managers surveyed over a period of 3 months, and input provided by the PICSE Task Force members as well as intergovernmental research organisations such as CERN and EMBL. The survey demonstrated that barriers to cloud service procurement mainly relate to the adoption of new technology (i.e. cloud computing) and the procurement process itself.

The first category encompasses legal jurisdiction impediments, which Eurostat [1] highlighted as one of the main barriers to the procurement of cloud services. Indeed, services are often hosted in one country and consumed in another, hence cloud consumers' uncertainty about data location and the applicable laws in case of dispute or in relation to compliance. Prerequisites such as expertise and knowledge of both contractual and operational aspects also impede the purchase of cloud computing services. The barriers posed by the procurement process vary depending on the type of process used. Restricted procurement processes suffer from a lack of competition and higher costs while open procurement processes are time consuming, require detailed specifications to be ready at the start of the procurement process and therefore lead to higher tendering and evaluation costs.

Cloud marketplaces and brokerage services are seen as aiding the procurement process but suffering from under-investment and thus not sufficiently mature. In addition, the nature of cloud services and the pay-per-use method can complicate budget planning for research organisations. Therefore, framework procurement agreements are perceived as a good alternative for the procurement of cloud services; along with PCP (Pre-Commercial Procurement), PPI (Public Procurement of Innovative solutions), and JPA (Joint Procurement Actions), which could potentially fulfil the needs of the research community.

To combat this situation and increase the uptake of cloud computing in the public research sector, cloud service providers (CSPs) are advised to increase transparency in their offers; particularly regarding security, privacy and data management, ensure the trustworthiness of their privacy policies and improve the Service Level Agreements (SLA) so that their offers stand out.

Similarly users are advised to acknowledge that the commoditisation of IT services that cloud services represents has economic advantages and that customisation of those services will increase procurement costs and potentially increase service provider dependence.

1. Introduction

Cloud computing has the potential to reduce IT expenditure and boost organisational agility while at the same time improving the scope for delivering flexible high-quality new services. However, the adoption of cloud computing services is inhibited by barriers related to procurement, perceived trustworthiness, technical standards and legal terms of reference, risk of vendor lock-in, etc. The overall challenge is to overcome these barriers in order to boost the public sector's productivity by stimulating the preparedness for wide adoption of competitive, secure, reliable and integrated cloud computing services.

The European Commission will launch a European Cloud initiative including cloud services certification, contracts, switching of cloud services providers and a research open science cloud. The work of PICSE is contributing to defining the research sector needs in terms of cloud service certification and contracts.

Public procurement represents approximately 19% of EU GDP and EU wide e-procurement is expected to save EUR 50 billion annually. The 2014 public procurement reform package foresees a transition to full e-procurement by October 2018. Increased efforts are needed to meet this target given that in many Member States the transition has started at a slow pace. The PICSE procurement model will contribute to the simplification of procurement by publicly funded research organisations [2].

This Procurement Barriers Report enables prospective buyers of cloud services and cloud providers to understand the new requirements and barriers introduced by cloud technologies in the existing procurement processes, and also to identify common challenges faced by the procurement actors (e.g. IT managers, procurement officers and legal experts), particularly those operating in the public sector.

The identified barriers are based on a collection and analysis of existing cloud procurement literature, online surveys, face to face and phone interviews and input from the PICSE Task Force as detailed in [Annex A](#). The relatively limited number of survey responses means the results derived correspond to a small fraction of the targeted community and should not be misinterpreted as being the outcome of a consultation of the whole of Europe's research community. However we would like to make the hypothesis that the level of response is representative of the current penetration of commercial cloud services in the public research sector.

Identifying the barriers that exist in procuring cloud services will lay the basis for building more appropriate procurement frameworks. The findings included in this report will be used as a starting point for the definition of a follow-up report on Cloud Computing Procurement Best Practices and feed into the PICSE procurement model.

1.1 Structure of the Report

This report is set out in the following sections:

Section 2 – Scope and Objectives of the report

Section 3 – Target Audience

Section 4 – PICSE Task Force

Section 5 – Methodology and Approach

Section 6 – Procurement Overview

Section 7 – Barriers

Section 8 – Next Steps

Section 9 – Conclusions

2. Scope and Objectives

The main scope of this report is to identify the barriers that exist in procuring cloud services for Research Organisations and better understand the best practices in procurement to minimise the impact of the remaining barriers.

The objectives of this study are:

- Understand the needs and requirements of IT Managers and Procurement officers when procuring cloud services
- Identify and analyse barriers in procuring cloud services
- Provide input for the definition of cloud service procurement best practices (D3.2) which will include:
 - A collection of procurement good practices in the public sector, both in Research and Public Administration, which would cover real life examples in Europe as well as outside the EEA,
 - A comparison between procurement practices in the public and private sector
 - A description of how current good practices can overcome barriers and the identification of unaddressed challenges.
- Provide input for the definition of the Procurement model by highlighting the aspects that should be taken into considerations by procurers and IT managers when procuring cloud (D2.2)
- Provide input for the definition of the Procurement Road Map (D2.3)

3. Target Audience

With the increasing IT needs for research and innovation, local, national and European public research organisations are moving into the cloud and so are the data they handle and work with. This means that many of them are either procuring, planning to procure or building private clouds with a view to forming a hybrid cloud with procured cloud services.

This report will help Research Organisations to understand the current barriers in procuring cloud services and the best practices in how to overcome those barriers. In particular, the key actors in the procurement of cloud services are among the beneficiaries of this report as explained below.

3.1.1 Procurement Initiator

The individual nominated by the management, usually with a technical background that has the responsibility, the technical competences and the budget to start and handle one (or more) procurement(s). He/she is the coordinator of the whole procurement process and responsible for achieving the support and buy-in of all stakeholders for the procurement process. He/she usually works in close collaboration with technical officers, procurement, contracts, and legal experts. He/she is charged with verifying that there is a corresponding approved programme and budget within its organisation, before starting the procurement action. He/she should have a strategic overview of the needs and of the procurement action. In the scientific and research community, IT managers often have a role both as a procurement initiator and as a technical officer.

3.1.2 Technical Officer (IT Manager)

An IT Manager is responsible for implementing and maintaining an organisation's technology infrastructure.

When procuring complex information systems, the IT manager needs to ensure that those systems meet business needs and function correctly in an operational environment. This means that the IT manager must be closely involved in the requirements identification, service agreement definition and negotiation.

Having a comprehensive inventory of known barriers can help IT managers understand the procurement issues and so better support the procurement office to purchase the most cost-effective and efficient system.

3.1.3 Procurement Officer

The procurement officer is the person who has a complete understanding of the procurement strategy and procedures of the organisation. He/she is responsible for the identification of potential suppliers, the procurement process (tender, price enquiry, etc.), the selection of a preferred supplier, the contract negotiation, the management of a contract, and purchasing processes.

By addressing procurement officers, we have uncovered examples of procurement practices, which provide feedback on the major barriers encountered.

This report can help procurers understand how to design their procurement model and how to address challenges they are facing (cf. Section 5 and 7), as well as help provide added-value services to members of associations of procurers and local governments.

3.1.4 Policy Makers

The procurement barriers registered in this report can be helpful to policymakers because they can be used as a reference point for developing policies for the successful procurement of cloud services.

3.1.5 ICT Vendor

The ICT vendor is the Cloud Service Provider (CSP). By understanding the difficulties faced by different procuring groups, CSPs can provide better offers for potential customers and also better respond to emerging requirements.

4. PICSE Task Force

The purpose of the PICSE Task Force is to act as a sounding board for the developments within the project, notably the procurement model, best practices and roadmap. The PICSE Task Force is a group external to the project, whose members were selected based on their international and wide-ranging experience in cloud procurement. The Task Force provides feedback and advice to the PICSE consortium.

The Task Force members are Martin Canning (IDC, a global IT research analyst), James Mitchell (Strategic Blue, a financial cloud brokerage), Linda Strick (Fraunhofer/Cloud for Europe) and Frank van Dam (Ministerie van Economische Zaken) and is chaired by Carmela Asero (Joint Research Center)¹. For more details about the members of the Task Force, please refer to the PICSE website².

The Task Force supported the PICSE team in identifying relevant documents for the literature review, in improving the structure of the online surveys as well as providing expert opinions during the analysis and conclusions.

¹ <https://www.linkedin.com/in/asero Carmela>

² <http://www.picse.eu/picse-task-force>

5. Methodology and Approach

This study is predominantly built on qualitative methodological instruments, namely literature research surveys and targeted interviews. Three online surveys were created for the purpose of this study. The first survey was launched in November 2014 and ran for 3 months with the goal of defining barriers in cloud procurement. After one month, the need of having focused surveys on procuring (i) IaaS and (ii) PaaS/SaaS cloud services emerged and two follow-on smaller surveys were implemented online and ran for 2 months.

The methodology steps followed are further described in [Annex A](#):

5.1 Literature review

The literature review was restricted to English language documents, with a focus on the timeframe 2011-2015, since Cloud Computing is relatively recent and has evolved at a rapid pace.

An extensive research of the available and relevant Procurement barriers literature uncovered documents such as an assessment and evaluation report, recommendations and research studies on Procurement, etc. which provided insights on how to build the questions for the surveys conducted. [3, 10-19, 22]

All relevant literature is reported in the References section at the end of the document.

5.2 Survey

From the literature review mentioned above, the survey was narrowed down to a total of 22 questions, the answers to which are the main data used for this report.

60 respondents took the survey, of which 43 answered a sufficient number of questions to contribute to the analysis for this report. At this point we would like to clarify that the analysis shown in the rest of the document corresponds strictly to the number of respondents and underline that the statistical percentages presented are not representative of the whole experience of research organisations or any other organisations since the number of responses is relatively limited. The percentages used depict the distribution of the answers given by the survey-monkey tool employed for each of the surveys: 43 answers for the extended survey, 15 answers for the survey on IaaS solutions and 5 answers for the survey on PaaS/SaaS solutions. The total number of options to choose from for a given question was at times larger than the number of respondents, which in turn caused the total number of responses to exceed 100%.

Questions 2 to 7 required the respondent to identify essential requirements in procuring barriers they have encountered in the process, as well as best practices they use or are aware of.

Questions 8 to 15 highlighted the respondent's concerns and perceived barriers to procuring cloud services and potential improvements to their internal procurement process.

The remainder of the questions determined the familiarity of the respondent with innovative procurement options.

In Annex C, where the results of the survey are shown, a table is presented in which all the questions and the information they provide are classified.

As stated at the beginning of the document, research organisations were the main target audience for this survey. However, some of the respondents were representatives of other communities such as governmental agencies, cloud customers (private companies), cloud service providers, funding agencies, policy makers, central government, consulting firms and non-profit IT organisations. These additional responses helped us position the public research sector in relation to other sectors (cf. Section 7, subsection 7.4).

Figure 1 presents a diagram of the demographic sample for all respondents and the sufficiently completed questionnaires. The first percentage in the graph corresponds to the completed answers and the second to the total. Note that the overall percentage of the answers may exceed 100% because a few of the respondents positioned their organisations in more than one category, e.g. Cloud Customer (private company) and Cloud Service Provider. In Annex C is shown the full number of respondents by category of organisation.

Figure 1: Respondents by Organisation

Figure 2, meanwhile depicts the role of the majority of the respondents in both cases: for all 60 respondents who started the survey and the 43 who completed it. Again, note that the overall percentage

of the answers exceeds 100% because a few of the respondents declared having more than one role in their organisations, e.g. Project Manager, Service Manager or IT Architect and CEO Etc. In Annex C is shown the full number of respondents by role.

Figure 2: Survey Respondents' Roles

Apart from the online survey, 3 interviews were conducted face-to-face (cf. Annex A:) while 10 respondents of the web survey accepted to participate in phone interviews and provide feedback to their online answers.

NOTE: Annex B includes the survey questions and Annex C the complete results.

6. Procurement Overview

6.1 Existing Procurement approaches

Currently there is no simple mechanism by which research communities in Europe can procure commercial cloud services to support their IT needs. The acquisition of cloud services is unlike most existing technology acquisitions in the public sector and procurement considerations should be a key element of the cloud acquisition process in order to reap the benefits of decreasing cloud costs, increasing performance through improved infrastructure, and enhanced functionality through system-wide innovation. [3]

Based on the information collected in the context of this report, we have ascertained that each public research organisation has its internal policies and procurement rules, which are usually dictated by the nature of the organisation. As emerged from the study conducted by PICSE on the procurement model³, the procurement process can be described in 5 major steps:

Figure 3: Five steps of Procurement Process

Despite the obvious similarities between the procurement of IT services in a traditional approach and cloud, procurement officers face challenges when purchasing cloud services, mainly related to the fact that cloud is meant to commoditise IT services and consequently the way IT services are produced and sold.

To help address these challenges and speed-up the procurement of cloud services, a series of initiatives are emerging in Europe:

- Cloud marketplaces

³ MS2 Procurement model: <https://zenodo.org/record/15688#.VO9MJU10yUk>

A cloud marketplace is an online storefront through which customers may subscribe to cloud services that are built on, integrate with or complement the cloud provider(s) infrastructure, platform or software service. Below are some examples of existing cloud marketplaces in Europe:

- **UK Digital Marketplace:** a U.K government program, also known as G-Cloud, aiming at easing procurement by public sector bodies and a government-wide adoption of cloud computing. The G-Cloud consists of:
 - A series of framework agreements with suppliers, from which public sector organisations can call off services without needing to run a full tender or competitive procurement process.
 - An online store - the "Digital Marketplace" (previously "CloudStore") that allows public sector bodies to search for services that are covered by the G-Cloud frameworks. [4]

The **Helix Nebula Marketplace**⁴, the **Deutsche Börse Cloud Exchange**⁵ and **Uber Cloud**⁶ are examples of the emerging trends of cloud marketplaces that are not initiated by a national government. The Helix Nebula Marketplace is a European Cloud Marketplace service that is compliant with EU regulations and legislation, created through collaboration between commercial providers and public e-Infrastructures. The Deutsche Börse Cloud Exchange is a marketplace for IaaS resources both for private and public sector, which enables trading of computational memory and storage and introduces standardized products and services.

- **Pre-commercial procurement** is reported to be a good model to understand the needs of the public sector. It is used by research institutes in the Cloud for Europe and similar EC co-funded projects and is an approach for procuring research and development services of new innovative solutions before they are commercially available. [5]

The survey gave us additional data to allow us to describe the process followed by research organisations as well as some public administrations. In particular, based on the answers obtained to Question 4 (see table 1) on the use of procurement best practices or standards for the procurement of cloud services, it results that each organisation has its own way of procuring cloud services, depending on its needs, sector of activity and geographic location. Typically such organisations:

1. Develop their own procurement practices or follow known procurement approaches.
2. Need to adhere to specific regulations (especially in Public Organisations).
3. Embrace standards (especially related to information security).

A range of procurement procedures is used in the public sector. These include the Open, Restricted, Negotiated and Competitive Dialogue procedures. Each of these procedures sets its own limitations on the procuring authority and hence, if the procuring authority has a choice of which procedure to apply, it must be taken into consideration. Adopting the most appropriate procedure can benefit both public purchasers and businesses, particularly small and medium-sized companies. [6]

⁴ <http://hnx.helix-nebula.eu/>

⁵ <http://cloud.exchange/en/>

⁶ <https://www.theubercloud.com/>

A summary of procurement procedures mentioned briefly by survey’s respondents is displayed in Table 1.

Type of Organisation	Examples of Procurement Process followed
Funding Agency, International Institution	EU Procurement process directives [6][20][21]
U.K Government Agency	Crown Commercial Service guidance ⁷
U.S based Private sector/ Cloud Provider	Procurement process making use of NIST Standards [24][25][26]
Research Institute	Pre-commercial procurement [5]
Cloud Service Provider	Procurement process making use of ISO/IEC 27001:2013 [27]
CERN, EMBL, ESA – intergovernmental organisations	CERN ⁸ /EMBL ⁹ /ESA ¹⁰ Procurement Rules

Table 1: Procurement Process by Survey Respondents

6.2 Needs and requirements

From the answers given in the survey, mainly deriving from questions 2, 9 and 16, the mostly expressed requirement is the **need for contractual transparency** in terms and conditions as stated from more than 48% of the respondents. The importance of this requirement can be inferred as a barrier statement as explained in Section 6.3.2.

Other requirements that are considered essential in the procurement of cloud services are monitoring the SLA, transparency in the supply chain (performance on quality of service, reliability of supply, etc.) and provisions for liability. Then follows data confidentiality and service benchmarking, as well as flexibility of the internal procurement process. Other requirements include open standards for procurement, legal compliance and data protection. The table below presents the top 5 requirements for procurement of cloud services.

⁷ <https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/crown-commercial-service>

⁸ <http://procurement.web.cern.ch/procurement-strategy-and-policy>

⁹ http://www.embl.de/aboutus/administration/unit_purchase/strategy_policy/

¹⁰ http://www.esa.int/About_Us/Industry/Industry_how_to_do_business/The_basic_principles_of_ESA_s_procurement_approach

Place	Requirements
# 1	Contractual transparency (terms of conditions) (48%)
# 2	SLA Monitoring (40%)
# 3	Transparency in the supply chain (31%)
# 4	Liability (31%)
# 5	Confidentiality (27%)

Table 2: Top 5 requirements for procurement of cloud services

Asked about **need for improvement**/concern in the procured services, almost 70% answered control over their data, followed by the need for well-defined privacy policies (58%), data confidentiality (51%) and clear description of SLAs (47%). Other requirements include definition and attribution of responsibilities (37%), Service Interoperability (35%) etc.

Question 16 asked about the kind of **innovation** they would like to see in cloud procurement, the answers included again transparency and standards on cloud-based services. The establishment of joint procurements and on the longer term a viable marketplace and/or broker model dedicated to the needs of public sector administration and science were seen as beneficial. Dynamic procurement platforms, which improve the procurement processes followed and adapting them to the organisation’s needs along with benchmark references to compare provider's capability, completed the list of answers to this question.

Figure 4 is a summary of the common requirements extracted from the three questions above. It depicts the link and repetition created by the expressed requirements that are considered as **Essentials, important in Innovation** and that **need Improvement**. As can be seen, **Essential Requirements** are seen as Confidentiality and SLA’s but at the same time they are considered to be in need of **Improvement**. While **Innovation** would be Transparency, which is also stated as an **Essential** requirement to procuring cloud services.

Figure 4: Needs and Requirements

It seems there is the need for a personal data framework agreement between public body and the procuring customer. The definition of an appropriate Service Level Agreement (SLA) is seen as necessary in order to

establish an acceptable legal framework for the service between the customer and the provider. Dialogue between demand-side and supply-side is very useful to identify the character of services needed and understand the conditions and readiness for it to be procured and delivered.

6.3 Challenges

6.3.1 Identification of challenges in IaaS, PaaS, SaaS

Cloud computing’s value proposition is derived from the fact that certain pieces of the hardware and software stack (or even components within a specific layer) are common enough to be standardized and deployed with little variance from one installation to another. This approach decreases acquisition costs and speeds up time to delivery, but also means that customers will have less control on the environment, and customizations can be costly or sometimes impossible. This latter becomes apparent in the move from IaaS to PaaS to SaaS and also if the cloud solution is a multi-tenant environment [7]

In the IaaS survey where the majority of the responses came from Cloud Customers (private company – 53,33%) the main reasons to procure IaaS solutions were TCO (Total Cost of Ownership – 60%) reduction and the building of a flexible infrastructure capacity (e.g. environments more interoperable and portable – 80%) as well as the reduction of provision time for infrastructure (60%).

Figure 5: Main reasons for IaaS solutions

Concerns were raised about the terms and conditions with vendors that are not easy to negotiate (40%) and lack of adequate international legislation for the establishment of the agreement. 40% of the respondents to these two surveys, state that there is no formal definition for Cloud and that suppliers and providers may use different definitions, and thus, different offers of quality service. This supposedly implies the existing ISO standards are not being applied. Therefore the major concerns raised were high cost of migration (40%);

including a risk of degraded performance (problems in the integration of existing infrastructure – 46.67%) but foremost the challenge of maintaining the confidentiality, integrity and availability of critical customer’s data (80%).

Figure 6: Migration challenges when procuring public IaaS

A solution would therefore be to establish the relevant benchmarking of service capability, security etc. (93,33%) as well as the existence of a cloud broker as an intermediary between the customer and cloud vendor (26,67%). Ending with the IaaS survey, it should be noted that lack of service interoperability (66, 67%) and lack of strict security controls (53, 33%) were underlined when trying to procure on public IaaS.

On the other hand, in the PaaS / SaaS survey where the majority of the responses came from Cloud Customers (private company – 60%) and Cloud Service Providers (40%), the main reasons for the adoption of both cloud solutions were TCO (Total Cost of Ownership) reduction (60%), financial flexibility/cost variability (40%) and operational agility (80%).

Figure 7: Main reasons for procuring IaaS-PaaS Cloud Services by organisations

Challenges and barriers were identified in both solutions. Compliance with personal data regulations (60%-100%), time-consuming procurement process (100%-100%) and lack of process standardization (100%-100%) were prominent. In addition, lack of information in the procurement process (End-to-end visibility in the procurement process), immature service marketplace & brokers and complexity of managing, securing and maintaining the dynamic environments (100%-66, 67%). Further challenges and barriers were identified in the survey; including lack of suitable solutions/service (100%) and lack of mature standards (66.67% - 100%) as well as the lack of exit strategies (50% - 75%). Moreover, the difficulty to satisfy legal compliance requirements (66, 67% - 100%) as well as integration challenges (33, 33% - 100%). Finally, security concerns (66, 67% - 100%) and the in existence of deep customization (100%) were raised.

Figure 8: Challenges and Barriers in IaaS - PaaS/SaaS solutions

Concluding the survey for both IaaS and PaaS/SaaS, it was suggested by more than 60% of the answers overall for future applications, that the standardization for SLA description and relevant tools/mechanisms for assessing and comparing services, need to be presented and utilised with a more simple and clear description of the service specifications and features (100%). The existence of a service Certification / Accreditation Ability to try the service before procuring, as well as multiple access points / easy accessibility and efficiently managed services were suggested. Finally, a cross vendor compatibility (100%), a pay as you use (only in PaaS survey) and a vendor contract negotiation.

6.3.2 Comparison of identified challenges in different communities

As mentioned previously in this report, security and reliability are thought to be two of the most common concerns for those that are reluctant to purchase cloud services.

This section provides a comparison of the identified challenges (deriving from survey questions 7) obtained from the answers given to the survey regarding the procurement process, not only by the scientific community but also by others.

Our analysis shows that the most common barrier identified by all target groups is that **Service Level Agreements are not clear**, well defined and comparable (46.5%), while **lack of common standards**, common rules and common agreements would enable a more standardised and harmonised approach to cloud computing (44%).

Difficulties in customising the service according to the client’s needs and requirements are another often reported barrier that result also in the non-definition of an appropriate SLA by almost 42% of the respondents, privacy policies are not clear, well defined and comparable (40%)

Additionally, from the clients’ side, it is difficult to define requirements, as there is the absence of the expertise (33%) and unbalanced negotiation power between CSP and Customer (33%).

Table 3 below presents the top 5 challenges identified by the representatives of different communities that have answered the survey and compares their importance to each field. Note once more that the percentages used are based on the responses of the 43 persons who chose to answer this question.

Community	Standard Terms and Conditions	SLA’s not clear	Privacy policies are not clear, well defined and comparable	The service cannot be customised according to the customer needs	Lack of service interoperability
Research Institute/University	50%	64%	57%	57%	64%
Government Agency	33%	33%	33%	0%	17%
Cloud Customer (Private Company)	17%	50%	33%	67%	33%
Cloud Service Provider	13%	25%	50%	63%	38%
Funding Agency	67%	0%	33%	0%	0%

Table 3: Comparing Challenges in different communities

Figure 9: Barriers in different Communities

This is interpreted as issues in Standards due to the immaturity in practice & market and lack of clear SLAs preventing faster adoption of the Cloud; not only by the scientific community but also by all target stakeholders involved in this survey.

Barriers in specific procurement procedures can be identified from questions 11 and 12. Asked about the existence of barriers in existing open procurement procedures, 62% reported that it is time consuming, while 54% mentioned that the exact specifications have to be ready at the start of the procurement process.

7. Barriers

7.1 Barriers of cloud computing vs procurement barriers

Barriers to cloud service procurement can be classified in two main categories: those strictly related to the adoption of the new technology (i.e. cloud computing) and those connected to the procurement process.

In the table below are presented the top 5 barriers in procuring cloud services.

Place	Barriers
# 1	Unclear SLAs (47%)
# 2	Standard terms and conditions (44%)
# 3	Unbalanced negotiation power (33%)
# 4	Difficult to define requirements (33%)
# 5	Unclear cost model (23%)

Table 4: Top 5 barriers in procuring cloud services

Standard Terms & Conditions and Unbalanced Negotiating Power can be considered interrelated as many cloud services providers will be reasonably inflexible on certain contractual or service elements as it is just not possible to meet the exact needs of every client.

While open and restricted procurement procedures are most commonly used for procurement of cloud services, there are barriers to procurement of cloud services regardless of the procurement process used. The most preponderant procurement barriers identified by all communities are:

- In restricted procurement procedures:
 - Number of providers invited to tender might not ensure genuine competition
 - Lack of competition leads to higher prices and less investment in innovation
- In the open procurement procedure:
 - Procurement process is time consuming
 - No specifications ready at the start of the procurement process
- In the current marketplace:
 - Cloud marketplaces are still not sufficiently developed as the services offered are limited in number and scope
 - Lack of transparency in procurement processes (e.g. the service / provider selection process is not clear) along with the lack of not meeting the customer’s requirements.
- In cloud brokerage:
 - 60% consider it as not mature enough
 - Only 28% are not familiar with the concept

Note that the above barriers are identified by all respondents (including those that have not yet procured) and they remain the same when considering only those that have already procured cloud services.

It could be argued that it takes time for the demand-side to understand what is available in the market and what might best fit their needs. Practical issues that can work against a successful cloud tender could be not doing enough preparation, being too vague (or too specific), not being commercially interesting due to the size of contract versus cost of responding to the tender. This may be influenced by the client’s ability to enter into a dialogue with CSPs and their willingness to display transparency.

Experts’ opinion on the current market status is that the supply-side is quite mature and that there is a huge number of service offerings available. This could indicate a lack of market understanding or information gathering on the demand-side and its subsequent consequences on the tender process.

While there are obvious barriers connected to procurement practices in organisations, innovative procurement actions such as Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP), Public Procurement of Innovation (PPI) and Joint procurement actions (JPA) are being considered as innovative procurement options, especially in the research community where the level of awareness on the existence of such actions is the highest (54%). However the opinions about their usefulness are split with approximately half of the respondents believing that those innovative procurement actions would fulfil their needs.

The table below shows the top 5 barriers related to risks of cloud computing.

Place	Barriers
# 1	Lack of customisation (42%)
# 2	Unclear privacy policies (40%)
# 3	Lack of service interoperability (37%)
# 4	Lack of confidentiality assurance in IPR management (33%)
# 5	Immature services (26%)
# 5	Stringent legal and regulatory requirements (26%)

Table 5: Top 5 barriers related to risks of cloud computing

Both cloud customers and cloud providers agree that the level of customisation of cloud services is limited. This may be explained by the fact that cloud services are cheap because they are standardised, while customisation comes at a cost and getting the exact service designed according to a customer’s requirements would significantly raise the cost. Therefore moving certain workloads to a cloud environment may not be the best option for all customers.

7.2 Perceived vs Experienced Barriers

The literature tends to depict barriers such as lack of trust and transparency in the marketplace in generic terms, but it is more difficult to establish in detail the potential impact of those barriers for a specific context: for the public sector or the private sector, in publicly funded research establishments or public sector administration as a whole, whether in or beyond Europe.

The results of the survey show that the main concerns (perceived barriers) in procuring cloud service are (1) lack of information security assurance, (2) increased dependence on CSPs and vendor lock in, and (3) the need to procure from several CSPs might make the service orchestration difficult. While in the private sector, another main concern is the loss of control over the ICT infrastructure / data. The respondents with no experience in procuring cloud services believe that (1) control over data, (2) service level agreements, (3) privacy, (4) service availability, (5) data confidentiality and (6) service interoperability are the areas raising their main concerns and addressing them would improve the services they are procuring.

Additional problems (perceived barriers) in procuring cloud services come from (1) unclear SLAs which are not well defined and comparable, (2) difficulties to define requirements. For the research community the unclear SLAs represent by far the biggest problem, followed by lack of service interoperability, unclear privacy policies, difficulties in defining requirements, unclear cost models, insufficient customisation capabilities based on their needs and unbalanced negotiation power between CSPs and Cloud Customer. On the other hand, in the public sector, the main problems lay in the lack of confidentiality assurance and IPR management, unclear SLAs and privacy policies, difficulties in defining requirements, stringent legal & regulatory requirements, and insufficient customisation capabilities on the customer needs stand as the main problems.

As opposed to perceived barriers in organisations with no experience in the procurement of cloud services, real barriers faced in procuring cloud services appear to be (1) standard terms and conditions and (2) unclear privacy policies. Unclear SLAs represented a problem for one third of respondents. For the research community, the lack of confidentiality assurance in IPR management and limitation of liabilities presented additional problems. In the private sector, the standard terms and conditions were not a problem, but the insufficient customisation capabilities based on the customer needs, unclear privacy policies, stringent legal and regulatory requirements, lack of service interoperability were issues. Main concerns for current users of cloud services and the areas for improvement of the services are (1) control over data, (2) privacy and (3) data confidentiality, showing that the list of real concerns is significantly lower for organisations with experience in procuring cloud services.

The figure below shows responses on the main concerns and areas of improvement in the procurement of Cloud computing services.

Figure 10: Main Concerns in Procuring Cloud Services

It is also important to ascertain whether the barrier is caused by external factors such as legislation, in which case resolution reaches beyond the scope of this project and the good practice would be to avoid or mitigate the effect. In many cases, barriers are perceived and can be overcome, however. The distinction between a ‘real’ and a ‘perceived’ barrier is important. Our final task is to establish where good practice responses exist, how they work and whether they would benefit other communities.

7.3 Legal and Technical barriers

Cloud for Europe, an EU-funded FP7 project, made an overview of the legal requirements and challenges that a European based public organisation has to face when adopting cloud solutions in a public sector environment. The main legal requirements and barriers for cloud adoption in the public sector can be summarised as follows (1) a patchwork of national conflicting laws resulting from local implementation of European legislation, with the European Data protection legislation as an area of focus, (2) fragmented and diverging national legislation in the public sector, with often no clear or even conflicting national legislation on whether data in the relevant domains can be transferred to a(n) (international) cloud environment, (3) national legislation discouraging the transfer of data to a(n) (international) cloud environment, (4) inappropriate public procurement legislation and (5) hesitance to transfer data to the cloud for reasons of national defence and state secrets and generally speaking extraterritorial enforcement and foreign intelligence gathering practices. [8]

Requirements	Barriers
Applicable Law	Lack of appropriate legislation if no mutual agreement exists
Jurisdiction & dispute resolution	Lack of appropriate legislation if no mutual agreement exists

Data protection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Scattered European framework ● Confusion around application of data protection legislation ● Specific requirements around sensitive personal data ● Challenges for determining the applicable law ● Inaccurate legislation relating to the qualification of cloud actors ● Additional requirements for transfer of data outside EEA ● Security concerns
Liability	Responsible actors and redress possibilities hard to define given the variety of stakeholders
Contractual framework	Terms and conditions provided ‘off the shelf’ by the Cloud Provider; no opportunity to negotiate and if so, time and cost consuming
Data portability	Uncertainty on retrieval of the data in case of incident, termination or bankruptcy
Interoperability	<p>Lack of interoperability at various levels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Collaboration between public sector actors ● Ability for IT systems and services to work together ● Cross-border collaboration towards the End Cloud User
Consumer related concerns	<p>Legal challenges to ensure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Consumer specific requirements ● Confidentiality of the data ● Appropriate intellectual property rights protection
Public Procurement Legislation	Inaccurate public procurement legislation
Specific public procurement concerns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Language requirements ● National sovereignty ● National security (restricted access) ● Lack of harmonization of legislation in various law domains (for example archiving) ● Lack of clear legislation allowing a transfer to the cloud (for example archiving, criminal and social procedural laws) ● Legislation or guidelines discouraging a transfer to the cloud (national defence and state secrets, medical law)
Government access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fragmented legislation on law enforcement (general and criminal files) ● No clear guidelines on intelligence surveillance

Table 6: Main Legal Requirements and Barriers for Cloud Adoption

There is the need to focus on scalable and sustainable instruments of use for Procurement to ensure legislative compliance and delivery of intangible values such as security and transparency in the supply chain.

The results of the survey show that unclear privacy policies present the biggest legal barrier in procuring cloud services. Besides privacy, two other major concerns are control over data and data confidentiality,

which are often part of requirements both in national and European legislation, and can therefore also be considered as legal barriers. Other main concerns are considered to be (1) lack of information security assurance, (2) increased dependence on CSPs and vendor lock in, and (3) the need to procure from several CSPs might make the service orchestration difficult. While in the private sector, another main concern is the loss of control over the ICT infrastructure / data.

Even though the legal barriers are on top of the list of barriers, they are followed by a number of technical barriers, which are again more related to the real and perceived risks of cloud computing, rather than to procurement practice in organisations. The main concerns are considered to be service level agreements, service interoperability and service availability. Insufficient customisation capabilities on the customer needs can also be considered as one of the technical barriers.

The adoption of cloud computing depends greatly on how the cloud can address concerns on security (confidentiality, integrity, availability), portability and interoperability. Cloud consumers need SLAs to specify the technical performance requirements fulfilled by a cloud provider. SLAs can cover terms regarding the quality of service, security and remedies for performance failures. [9]

While both legal and technical barriers are mostly related to the real and perceived risks of cloud computing, barriers directly impacting procurement practice in organisations are related to the use of current internal policies and procurement rules, which are not enabling easy procurement of cloud services. To overcome those barriers, which can be both legal and technical in nature, use of cloud services may require a change in internal procurement processes and standards. While organisations are using different procurement procedures, depending on their needs, each of these procedures sets its own limitations and barriers. Organisations will be able to lower those barriers through the adoption of new skills and competences by properly training all actors involved in the procurement process of cloud services.

7.4 Ranking of the challenges to procurement of cloud services

Based on the consolidated and analysed information, we can notice that the ranking challenges in the procurement of cloud services is different for organisations with no experience in the procurement of cloud services, as opposed to those with experience. Concerns are in control over data, service level agreements, privacy, service availability, data confidentiality and service interoperability. On the other hand, organisations with experience in procuring cloud services only have concerns pertaining to control over data, privacy and data confidentiality.

The challenges of organisations with no experience in the procurement of cloud services emanate from a lack of trust, as the highest ranked challenges are:

Rating	All organisations	Research community	Public sector
1	Lack of information security assurance	SLAs not clearly defined and hard incomparable	Lack of confidentiality assurance and IPR management

2	Increased dependence on CSPs and vendor lock in	Lack of service interoperability	SLAs not clearly defined and hard incomparable
3	The need to procure from several CPSs might make the service orchestration difficult	Unclear privacy policies	Unclear privacy policies
4	SLAs not clearly defined and hard incomparable	Difficulties with defining requirements	Difficulties with defining requirements
5	Difficulties in defining requirements	Unclear cost models	Stringent legal and regulatory requirements

Table 7: Ranking of Main Challenges for organisations with No Experience in Procurement of Cloud Services

While the list of challenges for organisations with experience in procurement of cloud services is significantly shorter, they are ranked as follows:

1. Standard terms and conditions,
2. Unclear privacy policies,
3. Lack of confidentiality assurance in IPR management (only for research community),
4. Limitation of liabilities (only for research community).

Across Europe as a whole, the attitude towards cloud-based services varies enormously. Initiatives such as Cloud for Europe, with which PICSE is closely aligned through the PICSE Task Force, have the capability to break down these barriers through their advisory and advocacy roles in the government sector.

8. Next Steps

Together with the case studies performed in WP2, the results of this report will serve as input for the PICSE procurement model (D2.1 Research Procurement Model (M9)). Identified procurement approaches will be further compared in different sectors and different geographies with a particular emphasis on the way they address the type of barriers identified. We will also highlight potential challenges likely to be faced in the future. D3.2 Procurement Best Practices Report (M16) will propose a procurement best practice suitable for the European Scientific Community in the light of those challenges. This report will include:

- A collection of procurement good practices in the public sector, both in Research and Public Administration, which would cover real life examples in Europe as well as outside the EEA (e.g. USA).
- A comparison between procurement practices in the public and private sector
- A description of how current good practices can overcome barriers and the identification of unaddressed challenges

These best practices can then be applied to WP2 as one of the dimensions of the procurement roadmap (D2.3 Cloud Service Procurement Roadmap for public research organisations (M18)).

9. Conclusions

Based on the analysis of the input collected through the review of the literature, surveys and interviews and the lack of responses to the survey, the conclusions drawn in this report do not apply to all of the targeted communities. It is worth mentioning that the below summarised conclusions are however in alignment with the existing literature on many points.

Research Organisations are now actively pursuing the benefits of cloud services and the main reasons for procuring cloud services are lower TCO (Total Cost of Ownership), shorter service provisioning time and operational flexibility enabled by cloud services. While contractual transparency through terms and conditions and SLA monitoring are considered as essential requirements in the procurement of cloud services, cloud customers are expressing concerns in the lack of information security assurance, which indicates a lack of transparency from CSPs.

CSPs should provide visibility into the security and privacy capabilities of their cloud services. It is of particular importance for a procurement officer to know how to satisfy the technical requirements and compliance needs of a certain organisation. Service Level Agreement (SLA) represents a trust item and a service differentiator, therefore it is considered as a key component of any cloud service agreement. While the concept of SLA is simple, the application, enforcement and monitoring are not. Only clear, complete and comparable SLAs by CSPs will increase the level of trust in the cloud computing services.

It can be said that main barriers to procurement of cloud services are coming from lack of trust, which is generated by a perceived lack of clarity in SLAs and privacy policies, standard terms and conditions and sometimes in the lack of maturity of cloud services and cloud marketplaces. Potential cloud customers in the research area, across public and private sectors are not always ready for cloud services as they are unwilling/unable to make the organisational changes necessary for the effective use of cloud services.

Indeed, the use of cloud services may require a change in internal procurement processes and standards since there are currently no simple mechanism by which research communities in Europe can procure commercial cloud services to support their IT needs. Every organisation has its own way of procuring cloud services, depending on its needs. While there are several different procurement procedures available, each of these procedures sets its own limitations and barriers. Until cloud marketplaces and cloud brokerage reach a satisfying level of maturity, the framework procurement agreements will remain a good option for the procurement of cloud services.

Possible solutions to overcome the identified barriers include the need to increase awareness and maturity on the demand side, as well as to introduce innovation in cloud procurement. Innovative procurement actions such as Pre-commercial procurement, Public procurement of innovative solutions and Joint procurement actions are also considered as innovative procurement options with a potential to meet the needs of the research community.

In order to reduce barriers related to transparency, information security assurance and a wider adoption of standards; especially for information security and SLAs, a number of actions have already been put in motion.

The work achieved by the EC C-SIG on SLA, Certification and Privacy Code of Conduct, the ENISA Cloud Certification Scheme List (CCSL)¹¹ and the Cloud Certification Scheme Metaframework (CCSM)¹² and by Cloud Security Alliance with its Security and Transparency Assurance Registry (STAR)¹³ is effective. For example, in December 2014 the European Commission opened a public tender for the procurement of cloud services for several European Institutions leveraging the work done ENISA in the CCSM and by CSA with STAR for the definitions of security objectives and the demonstration of their fulfilment. Generally speaking, the use of existing standards and certification frameworks can lift barriers to cloud adoption and make the procurement of cloud services more effective and efficient for the heavily regulated public sector.

Additionally, by increasing service customizability and contractual flexibility in terms of standard terms & conditions, CSPs would help overcome more challenges for the demand side. A viable marketplace and/or broker model is deemed as the best long-term solution for the scientific community and for all other target stakeholders involved in this survey.

Finally, as organisations are having difficulties with defining requirements during the procurement of cloud services, there is a clear need for the adoption of new skills and competences and it is the responsibility of the organisations to properly train all actors involved in the procurement process of cloud services.

¹¹ <https://resilience.enisa.europa.eu/cloud-computing-certification>

¹² <https://resilience.enisa.europa.eu/cloud-computing-certification/cloud-certification-schemes-metaframework>

¹³ <https://cloudsecurityalliance.org/star/certification/>

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Annex A:

Analysis of the Methodology and Approach

This study is predominantly built on qualitative methodological instruments, namely literature research, targeted interviews and surveys to support the experts' conclusions. Three online surveys were created for the purpose of supporting the conclusions of this study. The first survey launched in November 2014 and running for 3 months, aimed to define barriers in cloud procurement. After one month, the need for focused surveys on procuring (i) IaaS and (ii) PaaS/SaaS cloud services emerged and two smaller surveys were implemented. The latter were conducted only online and ran for 2 months.

The first extended survey was conducted through:

- Face to face interviews
- Internet surveys
- Phone interviews

Target stakeholders for the interviews were mainly public and private participants involved in public and private research activities and academic institutions, policy makers, government agencies, as well as representatives of public and private sector.

Appendix B of this report includes an analytic display of the respondents' sectors as the survey was conducted anonymously.

Interviewees were IT managers from leading European research organisations such as CERN, EMBL, ESA and ECMWF involved in Helix Nebula, The Science Cloud Initiative in order to overcome procurement procedures within research organisations cloud offerings unfit for their IT needs. Two categories were identified: 1) IT managers as users of IT services and therefore drivers of the cloud service procurement 2) Procurement Officers, as material executors of the procurement process.

In addition, targeted invitations to compile the survey were sent to key stakeholders to reach deeper insights on specific aspects, building upon and completing the information that was previously collected. Contacted stakeholders were organised in the following categories:

- Research Community: Scientists that have adopted or are looking forward to adopting cloud solutions
- Public/Private Sector Providers: Providers of cloud solutions (products and services), including service providers and users
- Education Bodies: Libraries that have procured or intended to procure cloud services
- Policy makers: European commission representatives
- Government agencies

The Internet surveys were conducted through [surveymonkey.com](https://www.surveymonkey.com/)¹⁴ and the links to the surveys were published in the Procurement Forum¹⁵, the PICSE website¹⁶ and social networks, Cloud Security Alliance website¹⁷, its LinkedIn account and CSA EMEA Chapter mailing list and the Research Data Alliance website¹⁸.

An amount of events where PICSE was presented were also used for the dissemination of the survey links. Open Standards for ICT Procurement¹⁹ and European Cloud Conference “Vision or Fiction”²⁰ are two examples of the events to which PICSE participated in 2014 and 2015.

Survey responses were aggregated and analysed on the phone and face-to-face interviews conducted; wherever possible and insightful, viewpoints from different market constituents have been contrasted.

The research methodology followed can be summarised in the following eight stages:

1. Identification of drivers and barriers in procuring cloud services through extensive literature review
2. Organisation identification as target group
3. Sample identification (who to invite from the target groups identified)
4. Email invitation
5. Web-based surveys
6. Phone interviews
7. Ranking / analysing method
8. Presentation of results

¹⁴<https://www.surveymonkey.com/>

¹⁵<https://procurement-forum.eu>

¹⁶<http://www.picse.eu/>

¹⁷<https://cloudsecurityalliance.org/surveys/>

¹⁸<https://rd-alliance.org>

¹⁹https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/community/open_standards_ict/event/open-standards-ict-procurement-sharing-best-practices

²⁰<http://www.afcea.org/europe/html/EuropeanCloud-Foreword.asp>

Annex B

PICSE Survey:

(PICSE: Procurement Innovation for Cloud services in Europe)

To ensure that Europe reaps the benefits of the shift to cloud computing, there is a need to focus on new ways of procuring cloud-based services.

The PICSE Procurer’s Platform will give access to a unique repository of information supporting the move from outright purchase to ‘pay-per-usage’ made possible by the arrival of cloud computing.

The goal of this survey is to collect information useful to identify challenges that exist in cloud procurement and to produce a report on cloud procurement barriers.

All answers are anonymous and will be used for collection of input and statistical conclusions only.

Please help us identify those barriers and get access to the ‘Procurement Barriers Report’ that will help you address obstacles of procuring cloud services.

General:

Your organisation:

a) Central Government (cabinet, ministry)	b) Decentralized government (regions, provinces, city, municipality)
c) Research Institute/ University	d) Government agency
e) Cloud Customer (private company)	f) Cloud Service Provider
g) Policy Group	h) Funding Agency (EC, etc.)
g) Other, please specify	

Your role:

a) Procurement Officer	b) IT Architect
c) Legal Officer	d) Financial Controller
e) Project Manager	f) Service Manager
g) Policy Officer	h) CEO
i) Consultant/advisor	j) Researcher / Academic
k) Other, please specify	

Question 1:

Did you ever procure cloud services?

- a) Yes
- b) No

Question 2:

What are the essential requirements in the procurement of cloud services?

a) Contractual transparency (terms of conditions)	b) Confidentiality (e.g. IPR management)
c) Transparency in the supply chain (performance on quality of service, reliability of supply, etc.)	d) SLA Monitoring
e) Liability	f) Flexibility of the internal procurement process
g) Service benchmarking (sufficient information about providers and their services)	h) Open Standards for procurement
i) None of the above	j) All of the above
h) Other, please specify	

Question 3:

What are the main reasons for your organisation to procure (or consider to procure) cloud services?

a) Financial: lower TOC (Total Cost of Ownership)	b) Financial: lower fixed cost
c) Shorter procurement process	d) Shorter service provisioning process
e) Pay as go self-service model	f) The expertise of the CSP
g) Gives to my company operational flexibility	h) Other (please specify)

Question 4:

Do you use any procurement best practices/standards? Please specify which ones and if they are general or specific to your business sector (e.g. Scientific community)?

(Open question)

Question 5:

Please briefly describe your procurement process:

(Open question)

Question 6:

In your opinion which of the statements below are relevant to cloud service procurement (*more than one answer*):

a) Shortage of skills among procurers	b) Absence of formal training of procurers
c) Lack of sufficient procurement expertise involving innovation	d) Unclear internal requirements definition
e) Lack of engagement between procurers and suppliers	f) The market of contracts brokers is still not mature enough
g) The market of technical brokers is still not mature enough	h) Cloud marketplace are still not sufficiently developed
i) Cloud marketplaces make the procurement of cloud services more effective and efficient	j) Cloud brokers make the procurement of cloud services more effective and efficient
k) Cloud brokerage might introduce new risks	l) Joint procurement process (e.g. organisation with similar needs joint procuring cloud services) are a useful tool to increase the bargaining power of the customer
m) The joint procurement process is not an efficient and effective solution	n) Current procurement best practices do not require any cloud adaptation
o) Current procurement best practices need to be reviewed to facilitate cloud adoption	p) There is a lack of decision-making support solution
q) Cloud service certification facilitate service procurement	

Question 7:

Which are the barriers / problems that you have faced in procuring cloud services? (*more than one answer*)

a) Standard terms and conditions	b) Unbalanced negotiation power between CSP and Customer
c) The service cannot be customised according to the customer needs	d) The number of services available / offered is limited
e) The services I would need to procure are still immature	f) Lack of confidentiality assurance in IPR management
g) The procurements process becomes cumbersome.	h) Our internal procurement capabilities / processes are difficult to adapt to the cloud computing procurement model
i) Difficult to define requirements	j) Lack of information about the service during the selection phase
k) Lack remedies and limitation of liability	l) SLAs are not clear, well defined and comparable
m) Privacy policies are not clear, well defined and comparable	n) Stringent legal and regulatory requirements
o) Lack of service interoperability	p) Unclear cost model (difficult to understand the real cost/benefit of adopting cloud services)c)
q) All the above	r) Other than above. Please specify.

Question 8:

What are your concerns (perceived risks and barriers) in procuring cloud service (please note that the proposed options are examples of both barriers to the procurement officers and to the manager/staff member that needs to use the service):

a) Lack of information about the service during the selection phase	b) Lack of CSPs transparency, e.g. information asymmetry between CSP and customer
c) Lack of information security assurance	d) The need to procure from several CSPs might make the service orchestration difficult
e) Increased dependence on CSPs and vendor lock in	f) Loss of control over the ICT infrastructure / data
g) Difficult to obtain good proposal in RfP and tenders.	h) Increased complexity and overhead in the procurement process (The overall costs generated by the procurement process would increase)
i) None of the above	j) Other. Please specify

Question 9:

As a current user of cloud services, what are your main concerns? What would improve the services you are procuring?

a) Privacy	b) Control over data
c) Governance (existence of the appropriate organisational structures, processes, and controls)	d) Service availability
e) Service Level Agreements	f) Data confidentiality
g) Compliance complexity	h) Service Interoperability
i) Service composability	j) Definition and attribution of responsibilities
k) Definition and attribution of liabilities	l) Other. Please specify

Question 10:

Please rank the following procurement approaches from 1 to 4, where 1 is the approach that best fit your need and 4 the least.

Please provide also rationale of your selection

a) Restricted procurement procedure	b) Open procurement procedure (e.g. Public tender and RFP)
c) Public marketplace	d) Public brokers

Question 11:

What do you consider as barriers / current limitation in restricted procurement procedure?

a) Procurement process is time consuming	b) High tendering and evaluation costs
c) Number of providers invited to tender might not ensure genuine competition	d) Lack of transparency in procurement process
e) Lack of competition leads to higher prices and less investment in innovation	f) Non-stimulative for private sector innovation
g) Inability to influence standards through procurement	h) Other, please specify

Question 12:

What do you consider as barriers / current limitation of open procurement procedure?

a) Procurement process is time consuming	b) High tendering and evaluation costs
c) Exact specifications have to be ready at the start of the procurement process	d) Dealing with uncompetitive and low quality bids
e) Enlarged market for certain services makes public procurement unmanageable	f) Non-stimulative for private sector innovation
g) Other, please specify	

Question 13:

What do you consider as barriers / current limitation of cloud marketplace?

a) Cloud marketplace is still not sufficiently developed (the service offered are limited in number and scope)	b) My requirements are not completely satisfied by the marketplace requirements
c) I don't have mechanism to understand if I can manage the risk of procuring cloud services from a marketplace	d) Disables full and open competitive selection and negotiation process
e) Loss of control through the service supply chain	f) Lack of transparency in procurement process (e.g. the service / provider selection process is not clear).
g) Lack of control over personal data	h) Other, please specify

Question 14:

What do you consider as barriers / current limitations of cloud brokerage?

a) I'm not familiar with the concept of cloud broker	b) The market of brokers is still not mature enough
c) Disables full and open competitive selection and negotiation process	d) More expensive than procuring services directly (The save of resources in the procurement process is lower than of the cost of intermediation)
e) Loss of control over service (e.g. performance, security)	f) Loss of control through the service supply chain
g) Lack of transparency in procurement process	h) Lack of control over personal data

i) Loss of control over aggregation and customization of services	j) Service arbitrage is inefficient
k) Other, please specify	

Question 15:

How do you continuously improve your internal procurement process?

0 Not at all 1 Partially 2 Medium 3 Good Correspondence 4 Full Correspondence

a) Conduction of customers' satisfaction surveys	b) Corrective actions taken based on customer's feedback and reported back to customers
c) Procurement staff understands the essential needs of the customer's needs	d) Documented procurement instructions manual made internally available to the customers
e) Regularly scheduled reports provided to customers that provides current and accurate status of the procurement platform they're in use	f) Documented annual business plan developed with department staff input and aligned with vision and mission of the procurement department
g) Existence of strategic plan supported by executive management and support by the allocation of resources such as budget, training opportunities etc.	h) Documented formal business continuity plan in case of business disruption
i) Defined and documented procurement accountability and authority	j) Procurement department staff receives adequate training in the areas of customer service, "soft skills", tools based skills
k) Automated third-party system exists to manage contracts, from the point of intake, through negotiation and to report retention.	l) 1% or less of contracts executed result in contract dispute within the 12-month period following contract execution.
m) Prospective vendors are qualified using a formal automated process	n) Vendor's performance is objectively measured using pre-defined metrics.
o) Cost avoidance/cost savings defined, measured, annual goal approved by management and goal met.	p) Other, please specify

Question 16:

What kind of innovation would you like to see in cloud procurement?

(Open question)

Question 17:

Are you aware of the following innovative procurement actions?

a) Pre-Commercial Procurement	b) Public Procurement of Innovation
c) Joint procurement actions	d) I'm aware of them
e) I do not consider them innovative solutions	f) Other (Please specify)

Question 18:

Do any of the innovative procurement options mentioned in Q17 meet your needs?

a) Pre-Commercial Procurement YES / NO – please specify	b) Public Procurement of Innovation YES / NO – please specify
c) Joint procurement actions YES / NO – please specify	d) Other please specify

Question 19:

The EC offers a PCP/PPI co-funded model for research procurement activities. Have you already considered this model? Do you plan to use this model in the future? If yes please provide details

Question 20:

What cloud deployment model would best meet your needs?

a) private cloud	b) public cloud
c) community cloud	d) hybrid cloud
e) other (Please specify)	

PICSE Survey on IaaS

Scope of the questionnaire is to identify procurement barriers related to commercial public cloud services (pay per use).

Note: Not repeating ‘General’ questions which are the same for all 3 surveys

Question 1: What are the main reasons for your organisation to procure (or consider to procure) IaaS solutions?

- a. TCO (Total Cost of Ownership) reduction
- b. Build a flexible infrastructure capacity (e.g. environments more interoperable and portable)
- c. Reduce provision time for infrastructure
- d. At a lower level of abstraction it allows to commit to a solution in the long-term
- e. Helps get lower prices
- f. Other, please specify

Question 2: What are your concerns about procuring IaaS solutions:

- a. No concerns
- b. Terms and conditions with vendors are not easy to negotiate

- c. There is no adequate international legislation for the establishment of the agreement (make sure it doesn't compromise the customer's rights/ restrict the cloud deployment from the providers part)
- d. There is no formal definition of the cloud. Suppliers and providers may use different definitions, thus, different offers of quality service
- e. Lack of budgets for new initiatives by the customer
- f. Other. Please Specify.

Question 3: Which of the following would you identify as challenges in the migration process when procuring public IaaS:

- a. High cost of migration
- b. Risk of degraded performance (problems in the integration of existing infrastructure)
- c. Challenge of maintaining the confidentiality, integrity and availability of critical customer's data
- d. Long provisioning time
- e. Other, please Specify

Question 4: In your opinion, what would be helpful in the providers IaaS model:

- a. First receive the services and then provide payment
- b. First pay for the services and then deploy them
- c. Existence of a cloud broker as an intermediary between the customer and cloud vendor
- d. Benchmarking of service capability, security etc.
- e. Other. Please Specify.

Question 5: What obstacles have you encountered in procuring/trying to procure public IaaS:

- a. I have never procured/tried to procure IaaS
- b. Lack of service interoperability
- c. Lack of strict security controls
- d. High cost of provisioning
- e. Other, please specify

Question 6: Do any of the innovative procurement options meet your needs?

	Yes	No	Not aware of
Pre-Commercial Procurement			

(please specify)			
Public Procurement of Innovation (please specify)			
Joint procurement actions (please specify)			
Other (please specify)			

PICSE Survey on PaaS/SaaS

Scope of the questionnaire is to identify procurement barriers related to commercial public cloud services such as Platform as a Service (PaaS) and Software as a Service (SaaS).

Question 1: What are the reasons for your organisation to procure (or consider to procure) cloud services?

- a. TCO reduction
- b. Financial flexibility (cost variabilization)
- c. Limited number of in-house resources
- d. Operational agility
- e. Other, please specify

Question 2: Which of the following would you identify as challenges when procuring? (multiple choice)

Which of the following would you identify as challenges when procuring	
PaaS:	SaaS:
a) Compliance challenges with personal data regulations	a) Unfriendly software with limited or no support
b) Lack of information in the procurement process (End-to-end visibility in the procurement process)	b) Lack of process standardization
c) No visibility in availability, price and delivery time of goods and services	c) Immature service marketplace and brokers
d) Time consuming procurement process	d) Complexity of managing, securing and maintaining the dynamic environments
e) Other, please specify	e) Other, please specify

Question 3: Related to question 2, which of the identified challenges become barrier to service procurement?

	PaaS	SaaS
a) None of them		
b) Compliance challenges with personal data regulations		
c) Lack of information in the procurement process		
d) No visibility in availability, price and delivery time of goods and services		
e) Time consuming procurement process		
f) Unfriendly software with limited or no support		
g) Complexity of managing, securing and maintaining the dynamic environments		
h) Immature service marketplace and brokers		
j) Lack of process standardization		
k) Other, please specify		
l) All of them		

Question 4: Are there any other challenges and barriers to cloud procurement, please select one of more:

	PaaS	SaaS
a) Lack of suitable solutions/service		
b) Lack of mature standards		
c) Security requirements that often exceed standard commercial practices		
d) No exit strategies		
e) Difficult to satisfy legal compliance requirements		
f) Integration challenges		
g) Providers are misaligned with the market needs		
h) Security concerns		

j) There is no deep customization		
k) Lack of budgets for new initiatives		
l) Other, please specify		

Question 5: What do you wish for better procuring ICT/ cloud services in the future?

	Paas	SaaS
a) Standards for SLA description		
b) Tools/mechanisms for assessing and comparing services		
c) Simple and clear description of the service specifications and features.		
d) Service Certification / Accreditation		
e) Ability to try the service before procuring		
f) Multiple access points / Easily accessible and efficiently managed services		
g) Cross-vendor compatibility		
h) Pay as you use		
j) Vendor contract negotiation		
k) Other, please specify		

Annex C

Key Survey Stats:

Extended Survey	IaaS Survey	PaaS/SaaS Survey
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All Respondents = 60 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All Respondents = 15 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All Respondents = 5
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Complete answers = 43 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Complete answers = 15 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Complete answers = 5
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incomplete answers = 17 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incomplete answers = 0 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incomplete answers = 0

Table 8: Classification of Extended Survey Questions and Information Derived

Questions	Information provided
Question first and second	Demographic identification
Question 2, 3, 9, 16	Identification of needs and requirements of communities
Question 4	Mention of Best Practices used by respondents for the procurement of services
Question 6, 8	Perception of barriers in cloud procurement
Question 7	Real barriers encountered while procuring cloud services
Question 11, 19	Identifying most needed procurement approaches
Question 11	Real and perceived barriers in restricted procurement procedure
Question 12	Real and perceived barriers in open procurement procedure
Question 13	Perceived (/real, if the respondent has experience and knowledge) barriers in cloud marketplace
Question 14	Perceived (/real, if the respondent has experience and knowledge) barriers in cloud brokerage

Question 15	Improvement/non-existence of internal procurement process
Question 17	Awareness of innovative procurement actions
Question 20	Identification of most suited cloud model according to organisation needs

Respondent Demographics for extended survey

Figure 1: Respondents by industry (survey monkey)

Answer Choices	Responses
Central Government (cabinet, ministry)	3.33% 2
Decentralized government (regions, provinces, city, municipality)	0.00% 0
Research Institute/ University	26.67% 16
Government agency	16.67% 10
Cloud Customer (private company)	10.00% 6
Cloud Service Provider	21.67% 13
Policy Group	1.67% 1
Funding Agency (EC, etc.)	6.67% 4
Other (please specify)	23.33% 14
Total Respondents: 60	

Full number of the considered 43 respondents by organisation:

Below are shown the 43 respondents classified according to all responses, full responses and those who gave the minimal responses.

Figure 2: Respondents by role (survey monkey): All 60 respondents.

Respondents by role (survey monkey): All 60 respondents:

Answer Choices	Responses
Procurement Officer	6.67% 4
IT Architect	15.00% 9
Legal Officer	3.33% 2
Financial Controller	0.00% 0
Project Manager	18.33% 11
Service Manager	8.33% 5
Policy Officer	3.33% 2
CEO	6.67% 4
Consultant/advisor	10.00% 6
Researcher / Academic	20.00% 12
Other (please specify) Responses	31.67% 19

Full number of the considered 43 respondents categorised by role:

Below, the roles of respondents classified in all responses, full responses and minimal responses.

Answers Statistics

Note that the numbering of the questions in Survey Monkey starts with the demographics question. This means that Question 1 in the survey is numbered as Question 3 in Survey Monkey and so on for the rest of the questions.

Q3 Did you ever procure cloud services?

Answered: 52 Skipped: 8

Answer Choices	Responses	Count
Yes	51.92%	27
No	48.08%	25
Total		52

Q4 What are the essential requirements in the procurement of cloud services?

Answered: 52 Skipped: 8

Answer Choices	Responses
Contractual transparency (terms of conditions)	48.08% 25
SLA Monitoring	40.38% 21
Transparency in the supply chain (performance on quality of service, reliability of supply, etc.)	30.77% 16
Liability	30.77% 16
Confidentiality (e.g. IPR management)	26.92% 14
All of the above	25.00% 13
Flexibility of the internal procurement process	23.08% 12
Service benchmarking (sufficient information about providers and their services)	23.08% 12
Open Standards for procurement	19.23% 10
Other (please specify)	Responses 19.23% 10
None of the above	3.85% 2
Total Respondents: 52	

Q5 What are the main reasons for your organisation to procure (or consider to procure) cloud services?

Answered: 52 Skipped: 8

Answer Choices	Responses
Financial: lower TOC (Total Cost of Ownership)	51.92% 27
Shorter service provisioning process	51.92% 27
Gives to my company operational flexibility	50.00% 26
Shorter procurement process	40.38% 21
Pay as go self service model	38.46% 20
Financial: lower fixed cost	25.00% 13
The expertise of the CSP	17.31% 9
Other (please specify)	9.62% 5
Total Respondents: 52	

Next 2 questions (Q6 and Q7) are opened questions and the answers given here are reported in Section **Error! Reference source not found.** in the report.

Q6 Do you use any procurement best practices/standards? Please specify which ones and if they are general or specific to your business sector (e.g. Scientific community)?

Answered: 22 Skipped: 38

Q7 Please briefly describe your procurement process:

Answered: 25 Skipped: 35

Q8 In your opinion which of the statements below are relevant to cloud service procurement:

Answered: 45 Skipped: 15

Answer Choices	Responses
Cloud marketplace are still not sufficiently developed	48.89% 22
Lack of sufficient procurement expertise involving innovation	44.44% 20
Shortage of skills among procurers	40.00% 18
Unclear internal requirements definition	40.00% 18
Joint procurement process (e.g. organisation with similar needs joint procuring cloud services) are a useful tool to increase the bargaining power of the customer	37.78% 17
Current procurement best practices need to be reviewed to facilitate cloud adoption	37.78% 17
The market of contracts brokers is still not mature enough	33.33% 15
Cloud brokerage might introduce new risks	33.33% 15
There is a lack of decision making support solution	31.11% 14
Cloud service certification facilitate service procurement	31.11% 14
Lack of engagement between procurers and suppliers	28.89% 13
The market of technical brokers is still not mature enough	28.89% 13
Cloud brokers make the procurement of cloud services more effective and efficient	28.89% 13
Absence of formal training of procurers	26.67% 12
Cloud marketplaces make the procurement of cloud services more effective and efficient	24.44% 11
The joint procurement process is not an efficient and effective solution	6.67% 3
Current procurement best practices do not require any cloud adaptation	4.44% 2
Total Respondents: 45	

Q9 Which are the barriers / problems that you have faced in procuring cloud services?

Answered: 43 Skipped: 17

Answer Choices	Responses
▼ SLAs are not clear, well defined and comparable	46.51% 20
▼ Standard terms and conditions	44.19% 19
▼ The service cannot be customised according to the customer needs	41.86% 18
▼ Privacy policies are not clear, well defined and comparable	39.53% 17
▼ Lack of service interoperability	37.21% 16
▼ Unbalanced negotiation power between CSP and Customer	32.56% 14
▼ Lack of confidentiality assurance in IPR management	32.56% 14
▼ Difficult to define requirements	32.56% 14
▼ The services I would need to buy are still immature	25.58% 11
▼ Stringent legal and regulatory requirements	25.58% 11
▼ The number of services available / offered is limited	23.26% 10
▼ Unclear cost model (difficult to understand the real cost/benefit of adopting cloud services)c)	23.26% 10
▼ Our internal procurement capabilities / processes are difficult to adapt to the cloud computing procurement model	18.60% 8
▼ Lack remedies and limitation of liability	18.60% 8
▼ Other than above. Please specify: Responses	13.95% 6
▼ The procurements process becomes cumbersome.	11.63% 5
▼ Lack of information about the service during the selection phase	9.30% 4
▼ All the above	4.65% 2
Total Respondents: 43	

Q10 What are your concerns (perceived risks and barriers) in procuring cloud service (please note that the proposed options are examples of both barriers to the procurement officers and to the manager/staff member that needs to use the service):

Answered: 43 Skipped: 17

Answer Choices	Responses
▼ Lack of information security assurance	51.16% 22
▼ Increased dependence on CSPs and vendor lock in	48.84% 21
▼ The need to procure from several CSPs might make the service orchestration difficult	37.21% 16
▼ Loss of control over the ICT infrastructure / data	34.88% 15
▼ Lack of CSPs transparency, e.g. information asymmetry between CSP and customer	32.56% 14
▼ Lack of information about the service during the selection phase	23.26% 10
▼ Difficult to obtain good proposal in RfP and tenders.	16.28% 7
▼ Increased complexity and overhead in the procurement process (The overall costs generated by the procurement process would increase)	13.95% 6
▼ None of the above	9.30% 4
▼ Other. Please specify: Responses	6.98% 3
Total Respondents: 43	

Q11 As a current user of cloud services, what are your main concerns? What would improve the services you are procuring?

Answered: 43 Skipped: 17

Answer Choices	Responses
▼ Control over data	69.77% 30
▼ Privacy	58.14% 25
▼ Data confidentiality	51.16% 22
▼ Service Level Agreements	46.51% 20
▼ Definition and attribution of responsibilities	37.21% 16
▼ Service Interoperability	34.88% 15
▼ Service availability	32.56% 14
▼ Definition and attribution of liabilities	32.56% 14
▼ Governance (existence of the appropriate organizational structures, processes, and controls)	27.91% 12
▼ Compliance complexity	25.58% 11
▼ Service composability	11.63% 5
▼ Other. Please specify:	9.30% 4
Responses	
Total Respondents: 43	

Q12 Please rank the following procurement approaches from 1 to 4, where 1 is the approach that best fit your need and 4 the least.

Answered: 40 Skipped: 20

Ranking					
	1	2	3	4	Total
Restricted procurement procedure	35.00% 14	15.00% 6	7.50% 3	42.50% 17	40
Open procurement procedure (e.g. Public tender and RFP)	35.00% 14	27.50% 11	22.50% 9	15.00% 6	40
Public marketplace	30.00% 12	32.50% 13	25.00% 10	12.50% 5	40
Public brokers	15.00% 6	30.00% 12	25.00% 10	30.00% 12	40

Q13 What do you consider as barriers / current limitation in restricted procurement procedure?

Answered: 40 Skipped: 20

Answer Choices	Responses
Number of providers invited to tender might not ensure genuine competition	55.00% 22
Lack of competition leads to higher prices and less investment in innovation	45.00% 18
Procurement process is time consuming	42.50% 17
Lack of transparency in procurement process	40.00% 16
Inability to influence standards through procurement	27.50% 11
High tendering and evaluation costs	22.50% 9
Non-stimulative for private sector innovation	20.00% 8
Other, please specify:	10.00% 4
Total Respondents: 40	

Q14 What do you consider as barriers / current limitation of open procurement procedure?

Answered: 40 Skipped: 20

Answer Choices	Responses
Procurement process is time consuming	62.50% 25
Exact specifications have to be ready at the start of the procurement process	55.00% 22
High tendering and evaluation costs	50.00% 20
Dealing with uncompetitive and low quality bids	42.50% 17
Enlarged market for certain services makes public procurement unmanageable	22.50% 9
Non-stimulative for private sector innovation	12.50% 5
Other, please specify:	7.50% 3
Total Respondents: 40	

Q15 What do you consider as barriers / current limitation of cloud marketplace?

Answered: 40 Skipped: 20

Answer Choices	Responses
Cloud marketplace are still not sufficiently developed (the service offered are limited in number and scope)	60.00% 24
My requirements are not completely satisfied by the marketplace requirements	32.50% 13
Lack of transparency in procurement process (e.g. the service / provider selection process is not clear).	32.50% 13
I don't have mechanism to understand if I can manage the risk of buying cloud services from a marketplace	30.00% 12
Loss of control through the service supply chain	30.00% 12
Lack of control over personal data	30.00% 12
Other, please specify:	15.00% 6
Disables full and open competitive selection and negotiation process	12.50% 5
Total Respondents: 40	

Q16 What do you consider as barriers / current limitations of cloud brokerage?

Answered: 40 Skipped: 20

Answer Choices	Responses
▼ I'm not familiar with the concept of cloud broker	27.50% 11
▼ The market of brokers is still not mature enough	60.00% 24
▼ Disables full and open competitive selection and negotiation process	7.50% 3
▼ More expensive than buying services directly (The save of resources in the procurement process is lower than of the cost of intermediation)	17.50% 7
▼ Loss of control over service (e.g. performance, security)	22.50% 9
▼ Loss of control through the service supply chain	17.50% 7
▼ Lack of transparency in procurement process	20.00% 8
▼ Lack of control over personal data	27.50% 11
▼ Loss of control over aggregation and customization of services	17.50% 7
▼ Service arbitrage is inefficient	7.50% 3
▼ Other, please specify: Responses	7.50% 3
Total Respondents: 40	

Q17 How do you continuously improve your internal procurement process?

Answered: 37 Skipped: 23

	Not at all	Partially	Medium	Good Correspondence	Full Correspondence	Total
Conduction of customers' satisfaction surveys	36.11% 13	13.89% 5	25.00% 9	13.89% 5	11.11% 4	36
Corrective actions taken based on customer's feedback and reported back to customers	21.88% 7	12.50% 4	21.88% 7	25.00% 8	18.75% 6	32
Procurement staff understand the essential needs of the customer's needs	19.35% 6	6.45% 2	29.03% 9	35.48% 11	9.68% 3	31

Documented procurement instructions manual made internally available to the customers	25.81% 8	16.13% 5	35.48% 11	16.13% 5	6.45% 2	31
Regularly scheduled reports provided to customers that provides current and accurate status of the procurement platform they're in use	32.26% 10	16.13% 5	32.26% 10	16.13% 5	3.23% 1	31
Documented annual business plan developed with department staff input and aligned with vision and mission of the procurement department	31.03% 9	10.34% 3	17.24% 5	31.03% 9	10.34% 3	29
Existence of strategic plan supported by executive management and support by the allocation of resources such as budget, training opportunities etc.	32.26% 10	12.90% 4	19.35% 6	29.03% 9	6.45% 2	31
Documented formal business continuity plan in case of business disruption	26.67% 8	16.67% 5	10.00% 3	33.33% 10	13.33% 4	30
Defined and documented procurement accountability and authority	24.14% 7	3.45% 1	13.79% 4	31.03% 9	27.59% 8	29
Procurement department staff receive adequate training in the areas of customer service, "soft skills", tools based skills	33.33% 10	6.67% 2	23.33% 7	26.67% 8	10.00% 3	30
Automated third-party system exists to manage contracts, from the point of intake, through negotiation and to report retention.	31.03% 9	10.34% 3	37.93% 11	20.69% 6	0.00% 0	29
1% or less of contracts executed result in contract dispute within the 12-month period following contract execution.	27.59% 8	13.79% 4	24.14% 7	17.24% 5	17.24% 5	29
Prospective vendors are qualified using a formal automated process	35.71% 10	10.71% 3	17.86% 5	25.00% 7	10.71% 3	28
Vendor's performance is objectively measured using pre-defined metrics.	31.03% 9	6.90% 2	24.14% 7	24.14% 7	13.79% 4	29
Cost avoidance/cost savings defined, measured, annual goal approved by management and goal met.	26.67% 8	13.33% 4	23.33% 7	23.33% 7	13.33% 4	30

Q18 What kind of innovation would you like to see in cloud procurement?

Answered: 20 Skipped: 40

Q19 Are you aware of the following innovative procurement actions?

Answered: 34 Skipped: 26

Answer Choices	Responses
Pre-Commercial Procurement	35.29% 12
Public Procurement of Innovation	23.53% 8
Joint procurement actions	35.29% 12
I'm aware of them	35.29% 12
I do not consider them innovative solutions	17.65% 6
Other, please specify:	11.76% 4
Total Respondents: 34	

Q20 Does any of the innovative procurement options mentioned in Q19 meet your needs?

Answered: 34 Skipped: 26

	Yes	No	Total	Weighted Average
Pre-Commercial Procurement	44.12% 15	55.88% 19	34	1.56
Public Procurement of Innovation	30.30% 10	69.70% 23	33	1.70
Joint procurement actions	52.94% 18	47.06% 16	34	1.47
Other	6.25% 1	93.75% 15	16	1.94

Q21 The EC offers a PCP/PPI co-funded model for research procurement activities. Have you already considered this model? Do you plan to use this model in the future? If yes, please provide details.

Answered: 22 Skipped: 38

Q22 What cloud deployment model would best meet your needs?

Answered: 34 Skipped: 26

Answer Choices	Responses
Private cloud	35.29% 12
Public cloud	44.12% 15
Community cloud	29.41% 10
Hybrid cloud	64.71% 22
Other, please specify:	11.76% 4
Total Respondents: 34	

Answers' Statistics for IaaS survey:

Q1 Your organization:

Answered: 15 Skipped: 0

Answer Choices	Responses
Central Government (cabinet, ministry)	0.00% 0
Decentralized government (regions, provinces, city, municipality)	6.67% 1
Research Institute/ University	6.67% 1
Government agency (can also be part of central government)	6.67% 1
Cloud Customer (private company)	53.33% 8
Cloud Service Provider	26.67% 4
Policy Group	0.00% 0
Funding Agency (EC, etc.)	6.67% 1
Other (please specify)	20.00% 3
Total Respondents: 15	

Q2 Your role:

Answered: 15 Skipped: 0

Answer Choices	Responses
Procurement Officer	6.67% 4
IT Architect	15.00% 9
Legal Officer	3.33% 2
Financial Controller	0.00% 0
Project Manager	18.33% 11
Service Manager	8.33% 5
Policy Officer	3.33% 2
CEO	6.67% 4
Consultant/advisor	10.00% 6
Researcher / Academic	20.00% 12
Other (please specify)	Responses 31.67% 19

Total Respondents: 60

Q3 What are the main reasons for your organisation to procure (or consider to procure) IaaS solutions?

Answered: 15 Skipped: 0

Answer Choices	Responses
TCO (Total Cost of Ownership) reduction	60.00% 9
Build a flexible infrastructure capacity (e.g. environments more interoperable and portable)	80.00% 12
Reduce provision time for infrastructure	60.00% 9
At a lower level of abstraction it allows to commit to a solution in the long-term	13.33% 2
Helps get lower prices	33.33% 5
Other (please specify)	0.00% 0
Total Respondents: 15	

Q4 What are your concerns about procuring IaaS solutions?

Answered: 15 Skipped: 0

Answer Choices	Responses
No concerns	6.67% 1
Terms and conditions with vendors are not easy to negotiate	40.00% 6
There is no adequate international legislation for the establishment of the agreement (make sure it doesn't compromise the customer's rights/restrict the cloud deployment from the providers part)	40.00% 6
There is no formal definition of the cloud. Suppliers and providers may use different definitions, thus, different offers of quality service	40.00% 6
Lack of budgets for new initiatives by the customer	6.67% 1
Other (please specify)	33.33% 5
Total Respondents: 15	

Q5 Which of the following would you identify as challenges in the migration process when procuring public IaaS:

Answered: 15 Skipped: 0

Answer Choices	Responses
High cost of migration	40.00% 6
Risk of degraded performance (problems in the integration of existing infrastructure)	46.67% 7
Challenge of maintaining the confidentiality, integrity and availability of critical customer's data	80.00% 12
Long provisioning time	13.33% 2
Other (please specify)	0.00% 0
Total Respondents: 15	

Q6 In your opinion, what would be helpful in the providers IaaS model:

Answered: 15 Skipped: 0

Answer Choices	Responses
First receive the services and then provide payment	20.00% 3
First pay for the services and then deploy them	6.67% 1
Existence of a cloud broker as an intermediary between the customer and cloud vendor	26.67% 4
Benchmarking of service capability, security etc.	93.33% 14
Other (please specify)	6.67% 1
Total Respondents: 15	

Q7 What obstacles have you encountered in procuring/trying to procure public IaaS:

Answered: 15 Skipped: 0

Answer Choices	Responses
I have never procured/tried to procure IaaS (multiple choices)	6.67% 1
Lack of service interoperability	53.33% 8
Lack of strict security controls	66.67% 10
High cost of provisioning	13.33% 2
Other (please specify)	0.00% 0
Total Respondents: 15	

Q8 Do any of the innovative procurement options meet your needs?

Answered: 15 Skipped: 0

	Yes	No	Not aware of	Total	Weighted Average
Pre-Commercial Procurement	13.33% 2	26.67% 4	60.00% 9	15	1.67
Public Procurement of Innovation	7.14% 1	42.86% 6	50.00% 7	14	1.86
Joint procurement actions	0.00% 0	42.86% 6	57.14% 8	14	2.00
Other	0.00% 0	50.00% 4	50.00% 4	8	2.00

Answers' Statistics for PaaS/SaaS survey:

Q1 Your organization:

Answered: 5 Skipped: 0

Answer Choices	Responses
Central Government (cabinet, ministry)	0.00% 0
Decentralized government (regions, provinces, city, municipality)	0.00% 0
Research Institute/ University	0.00% 0
Government agency (can also be part of central government)	0.00% 0
Cloud Customer (private company)	60.00% 3
Cloud Service Provider	40.00% 2
Policy Group	0.00% 0
Funding Agency (EC, etc.)	0.00% 0
Other (please specify)	20.00% 1
Total Respondents: 5	

Q2 Your role:

Answered: 5 Skipped: 0

Answer Choices	Responses
Procurement Officer	0.00% 0
IT Architect	0.00% 0
Legal Officer	0.00% 0
Financial Controller	0.00% 0
Project Manager	0.00% 0
Service Manager	0.00% 0
Policy Officer	20.00% 1
CEO	0.00% 0
Consultant/advisor	40.00% 2
Researcher / Academic	0.00% 0
Other (please specify)	40.00% 2

Total Respondents: 5

Q3 What are the main reasons for your organisation to procure (or consider to procure) cloud services?

Answered: 5 Skipped: 0

Answer Choices	Responses
TCO (Total Cost of Ownership) reduction	60.00% 3
Financial flexibility (cost variabilization)	40.00% 2
Limited number of in-house resources	20.00% 1
Operational agility	80.00% 4
Other (please specify)	0.00% 0
Total Respondents: 5	

Q4 Which of the following would you identify as challenges when procuring?

Answered: 5 Skipped: 0

	PaaS	SaaS	Total Respondents
Compliance challenges with personal data regulations	60.00% 3	100.00% 5	5
Lack of information in the procurement process (End-to-end visibility in the procurement process)	50.00% 1	50.00% 1	2
No visibility in availability, price and delivery time of goods and services	0.00% 0	0.00% 0	0
Time consuming procurement process	100.00% 1	100.00% 1	1
Unfriendly software with limited or no support	0.00% 0	0.00% 0	0
Lack of process standardization	100.00% 2	100.00% 2	2
Immature service marketplace and brokers	0.00% 0	100.00% 2	2
Complexity of managing, securing and maintaining the dynamic environments	100.00% 3	66.67% 2	3

Q5 Related to question 4, which of the identified challenges become barrier to service procurement?

Answered: 5 Skipped: 0

	PaaS	SaaS	Total Respondents
Compliance challenges with personal data regulations	60.00% 3	100.00% 5	5
Lack of information in the procurement process (End-to-end visibility in the procurement process)	0.00% 0	0.00% 0	0
No visibility in availability, price and delivery time of goods and services	0.00% 0	0.00% 0	0
Time consuming procurement process	0.00% 0	0.00% 0	0
Unfriendly software with limited or no support	0.00% 0	100.00% 1	1
Lack of process standardization	100.00% 1	100.00% 1	1
Immature service marketplace and brokers	0.00% 0	100.00% 2	2
Complexity of managing, securing and maintaining the dynamic environments	100.00% 3	66.67% 2	3
None of them	0.00% 0	0.00% 0	0
All of them	0.00% 0	0.00% 0	0

Q6 Are there any other challenges and barriers to cloud procurement, please select one of more:

Answered: 5 Skipped: 0

■ PaaS ■ SaaS

	PaaS	SaaS	Total Respondents
Lack of suitable solutions/service	0.00% 0	100.00% 1	1
Lack of mature standards	66.67% 2	100.00% 3	3
Security requirements that often exceed standard commercial practices	0.00% 0	0.00% 0	0
No exit strategies	50.00% 2	75.00% 3	4
Difficult to satisfy legal compliance requirements	66.67% 2	100.00% 3	3
Integration challenges	33.33% 1	100.00% 3	3
Providers are misaligned with the market needs	0.00% 0	0.00% 0	0
Security concerns	66.67% 2	100.00% 3	3
There is no deep customization	100.00% 1	100.00% 1	1
Lack of budgets for new initiatives	0.00% 0	0.00% 0	0

Q7 What do you wish for better procuring ICT/ cloud services in the future?

Answered: 5 Skipped: 0

	PaaS	SaaS	Total Respondents
Standards for SLA description	50.00% 1	100.00% 2	2
Tools/mechanisms for assessing and comparing services	100.00% 2	100.00% 2	2
Simple and clear description of the service specifications and features.	50.00% 1	100.00% 2	2
Service Certification / Accreditation	50.00% 2	100.00% 4	4
Ability to try the service before procuring	100.00% 1	100.00% 1	1
Multiple access points / Easily accessible and efficiently managed services	50.00% 1	100.00% 2	2
Cross-vendor compatibility	100.00% 3	100.00% 3	3
Pay as you use	100.00% 1	0.00% 0	1
Vendor contract negotiation	66.67% 2	100.00% 3	3